

CONCEPTUAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE PROCESS OF DEVELOPING RESEARCH SKILLS OF FUTURE ENGINEERS

Khuramova F.U.

Teacher at Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute (Republic of Uzbekistan)

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Abstract. *In today's high-tech society, engineering takes on a special place in culture. In this regard, the problem of training engineering personnel focused on the needs of innovative production development is being updated. Today, an urgent problem of technical universities is the training of future engineers in a way of mastering modern methods of searching, processing and using scientific information, mastering research methods, choosing new, more effective algorithms, resources, technologies within the framework of a competency-based approach. Today, there is a need to train a new generation of engineers who, along with fundamental theoretical training and a level of practical skills, possess research competence that contributes to the development of students' increased observation of phenomena of scientific interest, the ability to concentrate the work of their intellect on non-standard solutions to theoretical and experimental problems.*

Keywords: *research competence, research activities of future engineers, research work of students, project activities.*

Introduction. The need to constantly improve the quality of engineering training and insufficient attention to the problems of teaching technical disciplines in higher educational institutions determine the relevance of this study. Today, with the rapid development of technology, research skills are essential for every specialist. However, an engineer needs not only to know the general methods of conducting research, but also to be able to competently conduct an experiment using modern sophisticated equipment and materials. In the scientist–engineer–worker triad, which is necessary for the continuation of scientific and technological progress, it is the engineer who is the central figure of scientific and technological progress.

There is a need for public recognition of the importance of engineering and for changing the principles, methods and approaches related to building an engineering education system. Consideration of the nature of the research abilities of future engineers made it possible to scientifically substantiate the process of developing their research skills in universities. The study of the innovative development of vocational education at the present stage allows us to draw the following conclusions: there is a need to rethink the substantive and procedural characteristics of the research abilities of future engineers in the context of humanization, technology, information, integration and other trends in the development of vocational and pedagogical education. The formation of a learning goal that determines the direction and content of the process under study is the basis for clarifying the process of training future engineers. The tasks reflect the expected results of the process of developing the research skills of a future engineer.

Tasks of developing the research skills of future engineers: - general and special knowledge, research skills, formation of a scientific worldview and continuous development of personal and professional qualities, improvement of future professional activities; - development of the professional culture of the future specialist.

The main stages of the process of forming the research skills of a future engineer are based on the logic of scientific research of pedagogical objects and include the following sequence of actions:

- formation of goals and objectives of the stages of preparation for research activities;
- the study the essence and structure of the research abilities of future engineers and the features of readiness for them;
- development of the main stages of preparation for research activities;
- development of basic technologies, tools, forms of development of research skills of future engineers;
- determination of the conditions and requirements for the implementation of the preparatory process, taking into account the uniqueness of innovative processes in pedagogical education.

The conceptual justification should take into account the novelty of the content and structure of problem solving and the basic idea expressed by several rules that have an important commonality for research. A special methodological degree equips practitioners who use these research results in practice with the necessary mechanisms for their implementation. The description of the process according to the scheme "Conceptual and didactic support - special methodological description" creates a complete picture of the object under study, is well perceived in practice and has a high rate of implementation into real educational processes.

We determine the place of these theoretical approaches in the study of the process of formation of research skills of future engineers. A systematic approach is an approach in which the subject and phenomenon are considered as parts or elements of a clear holistic education. The elements are characterized by various interactions and connections within the object and in the external environment. A systematic approach in pedagogy has been developed by some educational scientists [1]. The teacher-directs the methodology for the development of students' research abilities and creates conditions for effective self-control and feedback of the student, regulation of student's research abilities, forms, methods and means of its organization, guarantees the introduction of changes.

The monitoring component involves an assessment of the results achieved by teachers and students, and a self-assessment process. As a rule, at the very beginning of solving research tasks, the student realizes at least one of the following situations - that the real level of knowledge is lower than necessary; the real level of qualification is lower than required; the amount of real funds is less than necessary. The formation and development of creative activity is a task that can be solved in stages. Personal activity is formed and developed under the influence of various, that is, educational scientific products, creative activities. The main differences between educational activities and the methodology of developing research skills are, first of all, the goals, the subject and the results of their implementation. In the process of developing research skills, the personal characteristics and qualities of a student researcher are formed.

The methodology of preparing students for research skills has a number of features, among which the priority ones are (see Fig.1):

On the basis of an integrative-developmental approach, it is possible to demonstrate the influence of personal qualities on educational, extracurricular and research abilities, while the following research qualities of a university specialist can be distinguished with:

- a motivational quality that characterizes a person's attitude to scientific and research abilities (the degree of formation of research interest, the desire to succeed in this type of activity and the degree of striving for it);
- operational qualities (mental techniques and operations used by a person in scientific research);
- active qualities (the ability to rationally use various sources of information in their work and optimally manage the process of independent education);
- communicative qualities characterizing the skills and abilities of students to use methods of cooperation in the process of research activities;
- evaluative qualities (mastery of reflexive methods of evaluating one's own activities).

Figure 1. Model of the method of preparing students to acquire research skills.

Literature analysis. In modern conditions, the concept of "engineer" is interpreted in different ways. For example, in the dictionary of S. I. Ozhegov, the concept of "engineer" is interpreted as "a specialist with higher technical education". In our opinion, this definition does not sufficiently reflect the specifics of engineering, but it makes it clear that an engineer should

receive a higher education. The authors S. A. Lebedev, V. I. Medvedev, O. P. Semenov [3] consider an engineer as a subject of technical activity. Engineering is closely related to engineering and technology, the development and direct creation of technical systems, their operation and management. Therefore, an engineer: "and there is a specialist who solves the problems of design, construction, functioning, practical application of technology on a scientific basis" [Ibid., p. 15]. V. J. Martinkus proposes the following classification of engineering activities by intellectual functions: managerial (organizational), design, technological, and A.I. Rakitov examines the process of modification of engineering activity with its inception and in a modern context. By engineering, he understands "analysis, continuous improvement and organization of individual and group work, production management, technological processes, design and engineering of products and tool systems" [5, p. 91].

The results of the study. We used methods of forming students' research skills using mobile technologies, including:

Mobile polling and voting methods, this method allows you to conduct testing or formative assessment and collect data from the entire audience, rather than from individual students. Instant feedback allows you to track the progress or difficulties in learning each student's material in real time.

The purpose of the method:

- knowledge control outside the classroom. Create a discussion based on the survey results.

Terms of use of the method:

- software for mobile surveys on student devices or - availability of access to cloud survey forms, or

- individual response cards.

Teacher's activity:

- preparation of the database of questions; - plan the sequence of asking questions; - monitoring the progress of the examination.

Student activities:

- to form your own answer to questions based on the studied material and your own judgments.

The method of control of the result and the criterion of its achievement:

- involving students in the voting process; - registration of students' level of training in real time; - the opportunity to immediately discuss the results of the survey.

The mobile search method. Searching and working with a variety of information is one of the most important skills of a modern specialist of any profile. Mobile devices with Internet access open up additional possibilities for information search due to the possibility of using voice and image search in addition to text queries. Based on this, it is better to encourage the use of mobile devices for educational purposes than to prohibit them.

The purpose of the method:

- mastering the work with information and communication technologies. Assimilation of new information.

Terms of use of the method:

- Availability of access to Internet resources and search services.

Teacher's activity:

- creating problematic situations that require the search for additional information to solve them.

Student's activity: choosing the best search methods and services; - search for a solution to a problem or issue.

The method of control of the result and the criterion of its achievement: - students' mastering of mobile search technology.

The method of mobile projects. Mobile devices and cloud technologies allow you to organize project activities at a new level, as they provide both new tools that are always at hand and a convenient organizational form. For example, most smartphones have built-in tools such as compass, navigator, map, camera, flashlight, etc. In turn, cloud-based data storage allows for a quick exchange of information between a group of students and a teacher. In addition, the development of mobile applications is of great interest among students due to their widespread use.

The purpose of using the method:

- performing individual and group design and research work.

Terms of use of the method:

- availability of mobile devices as target platforms;

- the presence of mechanisms for remote interaction between the student and the teacher.

Teacher's activity:

- organization of students' project and research activities;

- providing assistance to students in achieving the goals of project work. Student activities:

- solving design and research tasks (individually and as part of group work). The method

of control of the result and the criterion of its achievement:

- participation of students in the development of research projects related to mobile technologies.

Method of WEB QUEST. Studies of students' free time have shown that they spend most of their time playing online games. One of the most popular genres of Internet games is quest - participation in games using a computer and the Internet. Quest (from the English word "quest" — "search") is a game genre that requires the player to solve spiritual problems in order to advance through the plot. According to the level of reality, quests are divided into real and virtual ones. In recent years, the idea of forming new competencies, new types of literacy has emerged, which shows the general patterns of socio-cultural adaptation of technological innovations, the widespread use of digital mobile communications - a new form of social communication among students, it should be noted that the main features are the spatial and temporal continuity of communicative actions, on the one hand, and social communication using technical mediation, on the other hand, tends to individualize. For analysis, we consider the following research

1. What is the level of mobile communication usage among students?

2. What is the level of use of ordinary mobile phones (not connected to the Internet) and smartphones by students?

3. What is the function of using mobile communication for Uzbek students? What are these functions?

4. Is there a difference in the intensity of involvement in information and communication processes between students who have smartphones and those who do not?

The following hypotheses were tested:

1. The degree of mobile phone use among students is high — they use it often.
2. The level of use of ordinary mobile phones (not connected to the Internet) is lower than the level of use of smartphones by students.
3. The use of mobile communication facilities by students is characterized by wide functionality.
4. There is a difference in the intensity of participation in information and communication processes between students who have smartphones and those who do not have them - the intensity is higher for students using smartphones.

This issue was studied at a qualitative level in a free conversation among students, questions were asked about how students use mobile communication. The result of an anonymous survey conducted among students (Table 1)

Table 1

The use of Internet services during the month by students who have a regular cell phone and have a smartphone	in %
Visiting social networks	38%
Listening and downloading music	32%
Viewing and posting photos	21%
Communication on forums, in chat rooms, etc.	12%
News, events, sports, weather	48%
Watching and downloading videos	30%
Use of educational services	55%
Hobbies (visiting specialized websites)	21%
Reading books via the Internet, downloading	23%
Online games	21%

Students who had a smartphone used the Internet more actively than those who did not have a smartphone. In all ten positions, the percentage of smartphone owners who reported a particular feature was higher and ranged from 4.3% to 33.2%. The maximum is for the use of educational services (55%), the minimum (if you do not take into account the "other" position) is for communication on forums, chat rooms, etc. (12%).

Mobile device usage among students. During the study, the following research abilities of future engineers were identified:

- analytical and research skills (collecting information for research, separation of problems and conflicts, analysis of phenomena and processes of pedagogical existence);
- modular and predictive skills (the future of research skills: developing an image of an object, setting a problem, choosing a scientific direction, identifying the main organizers of scientific research, defining the goals and objectives of scientific research, taking into account the state of science and the needs of practice);
- organizational and methodological skills (planning of experimental work, development of a research program, development of general and private research methods);
- professional research skills (research activities, analysis of information received, generalization of new information, systematization);
- reflexive and evaluative skills.

Conclusion. Thus, the developed process of forming the research skills of future engineers corresponds to the set training goals, is characterized by consistency, continuity, interactivity, manufacturability, and takes into account the specifics of innovative processes in modern professional education. The main idea of the educational process at the conceptual level reflects the need to prepare for scientific and pedagogical, scientific and technical, scientific and industrial activities, this process is presented through approaches and principles that form the basis of general didactic illumination, a specially methodical image includes a description of the content, technology, tools, forms of motivational-targeted, cognitive-cognitive, operational-active, procedural-creative, reflective-evaluative stages of preparation, indicating the conditions for the implementation of the proposed process in practice.

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